

Effect of Knowledge of Tender Process on Access to Government Procurement Opportunities by Women, Youths and People Living with Disability in Ol-Kalou Sub-County, Kenya

Veronicah Kibari¹, Prof. Willy Muturi²

¹ School of Business, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

² School of Business, Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology

Abstract: The study sought to determine the effects of knowledge of tender process on access to government procurement opportunities by women, youths and people living with disability in Ol-kalou Sub-county, Kenya. The study was guided by; The Kraljic Portfolio Purchasing Model. This study employed descriptive research design. The target population of the study was 281 women, youth and persons with disability belonging to groups in Ol-kalou Sub-county. A sample of 165 respondents was drawn using Yamane's (1967) formula for calculating the sample size. Structured questionnaires were used to collect data which were tested for validity and reliability. Data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Data analyzed was discussed in form of descriptive and inferential statistics and presented in tables. The results indicated that the knowledge of the tender process had significant relationship with access to government procurement opportunities in Ol-Kalou Sub-county in Kenya.. Therefore the study concluded that the knowledge of tender process had a significant influence on access to government procurement opportunities by WYPD in Ol-Kalou Sub-county in Kenya. The study therefore recommended that the county government enhance means by which information in regard to tendering is made available to this group.

Keywords: Government Procurement Opportunities, Knowledge Of Tender Process, People Living with Disability, Women, Youths

I. INTRODUCTION

The involvement of vulnerable populations in public procurement is a fundamental assignment of all governments across the world [1]. Nevertheless, quite a significant number of countries have not been able to set in place actionable processes to ensure that procurement undertakings are transparent and aggressively advocate for fair and equal treatment [2]. The report by World bank further observed that there are no established in these countries to ensure that resources are connected to procurement in the public in addition to harmony with projected purposes; procurement staff are principled and held responsible and encourage public examination. [3] hypothesize that the duty of enhanced legislation in empowering women is being able to acquire public procurement prospect has been demonstrated to be flourishing around the world. Conversely, individuals with extraordinary interests are more liable to being ignored by the government and more prone to lack of skills and understanding owing to pitiable implementation of policies.

Governments are the chief volume purchasers of products and services in every part of the world. The reasons for procurement in public institutions is plummeting costs, gratifying the shoppers in regard to cost, time and value, conducting commerce with truthfulness fairness and earnestness and gathering public goals [4]. Public procurement systems are vital to the success of development expenditure. Public procurement signifies the method where goods, works and services are purchased by governments. Most advanced countries consume almost 20% of their GDP (Gross domestic product) on open procurement while emerging countries consume up to 50% [5].

A case in point is in the United States, Centralized public procurement for the period of 2009 consumed well above \$534 billion (Federal Procurement Data System, 2011) and well above 13% of the overall federal budget. It is viewed that public procurement is goal oriented and competent way of contracting between the state and private entities (Schooner, 2012) and is extensively used to stimulate socio-fiscal improvement objectives of a country, including the fiscal empowerment of underprivileged social groups [6]. Involvement of these underprivileged neighborhood set ups in procurement in Public institutions is an indispensable responsibility of any government in particular for an assortment

of reasons [1]. Basically, according to [7] rough estimations of the fiscal activities in the government procurement concerning the youths across the world fall under 10% -30% of GNP. At first, the impact of unfortunate persons in procurement initiatives has a well-defined effect on fiscal status of a country and requires being considered in the most excellent way.

In Africa, priority is placed on the deprived groups such as the personnel with incongruity, youth, and women; it is gradually taking form in Africa through ratification of several procurement regulations. The status of procurement in government significantly determines the governance and performance of community services and transcends through nearly all areas of planning, program management, and budgeting. In Malawi, the same case happens where a corollary scheme is being implemented to the ICT segment for procurements less than BWP 300,000 (US\$ 46,000), where a chance to tender is set aside, 100% for citizen-owned companies [8].

It is therefore, an essential market in any economy since it takes a considerable proportion of public income of a country [9]. In South Africa, the blacks are given preference in an effort to allow for various group distinctions, including the right to reimbursement for past segregations and also the predisposed groups in the society are given the power.

1.1. Global Perspectives on Government Procurement Opportunities

Public bodies have always been big purchasers, dealing with huge budgets. Public procurement represents 18.42% of the world GDP [10]. In Brazil, for instance, a new legislation introduced in 2006 provided special treatment for MSEs. The Brazilian Government faced a new paradigm: to buy of prominent and strategic segments in order to promote the sustainable social and economic development. The new legislation was capable of increasing the MSEs participation in public procurement to 30% of the total government's purchases and in 500% in value in a four year period [11]. Worldwide, public procurement has become an issue of public attention and debate, and has been subjected to reforms, restructuring, rules and regulations

Transparency and accountability in public procurement (PP) is currently at the forefront of India's political agenda, with the recent stalling of the Anti-Corruption Bill in parliament. In February 2011, the Indian Cabinet Secretary set up a special committee on procurement. The committee recommended increased transparency in the PP process and making procurement information accessible to the public [12]. The Indian parliament has introduced key legislation and initiatives to combat corruption in public procurement. Among them is the Prevention of Corruption Act of 1988 under which there have been disappointingly few convictions. On the other hand, the Right to Information Act (2005) has helped uncover many discrepancies in public finances. Transparency International India also created an Integrity Pact in the 1990s, a memorandum of understanding (MoU) between government agencies and potential bidders to reduce or eliminate the potential for corrupt practices in the bidding for and delivering of a government tender [13].

Australia's government 'encourages competitive markets, adhering to non-discriminatory purchasing practices, using efficient, effective, ethical and transparent procurement processes.' The government also 'encourages good practices from its suppliers expecting that they comply with Australian laws'. The Government of Australia also makes transparency and accountability a priority and strives to ensure that the public is always aware of how its money is being spent [5].

In 2002, Jamaica passed a Policy on Public Sector Procurement, which authorizes the Jamaican government to use its purchasing power to stimulate local producers and to use government contracts as part of a national development strategy. Government of Jamaica Procurement Procedures are determined and disseminated by the Cabinet of the Government of Jamaica. The Office of the Contractor General (OCG) exists in an auditory capacity and fulfils a transparency function because its concern is in monitoring and investigating awards and terminations of government contracts and ensuring that these contracts have been carried out in compliance with the relevant procurement procedure [14].

1.2. Regional Perspectives on Government Procurement Opportunities

In South Africa, preferential treatment is given to the blacks in an attempt to accommodate group differences, encompass the right to reparation for past inequalities and to uplift vulnerable groups in society. Similarly in Malawi, a reservation scheme is currently being applied to the ICT sector for procurement below BWP 300,000 (US\$ 46,000), where the opportunity to bid is reserved for 100% citizen-owned companies [8]. Women are the backbone of rural economies in Africa. Preferential treatment to the disadvantaged groups, among them the youth, women and persons with disabilities, is slowly taking shape in Africa through enactment of various procurement laws [15].

For instance, public procurement accounts for 60% in Kenya, 58% in Angola, 40% in Malawi and 70% of Uganda's public spending [16]. This is very high when compared with a global average of 12-20 % [17]. In developing countries, public procurement is increasingly recognized as essential in service delivery [16], and it accounts for a high proportion of total expenditure. The importance of government procurement in South Africa (SA) is illustrated by the fact that it has been

afforded constitutional status, including the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa of 1996, Public Finance Management (PFMA) Act 1 of 1999 and Preferential Procurement Framework Act (PPFA) [18]. According to [18] the Constitution of the Republic of SA of 1996, in section 217, provides guidelines on public procurement, and authorizes preferential procurement to advance certain groups that were previously discriminated. The Constitution obligates that the public procurement system of SA must adhere to fair, equitable, transparent, competitive and cost effective. Government procurement is therefore of huge significance. Government is responsible for ensuring that procurement policy supports and attains to overall economic objectives [18].

Upon all the benefits Ghana gain through procurement; the state is still challenged in so many ways. To operationalize the concept of good governance and to push towards “zero tolerance” of corrupt practices, the Public Procurement Act, 2003 (Act 663) was enacted by the government of Ghana to address the real and perceived weaknesses in the public procurement of goods, works and services. The main objective of passing the procurement Act (Act. 663) in 2003 is to eliminate corruption in the procurement process, regulating expenditure and also instilling discipline in public finances. [19].

In Egypt, where public procurement makes up a significant portion of the economy and has the potential to play a major role in incentivizing SME growth, collusive tendering (bid rigging) corruption and in-transparency remain serious obstacles for SMEs. In developing countries where corruption is still a pervasive issue, transparency initiatives are critical to unlock many challenges facing SMEs in benefitting from the public procurement market especially those owned by women. Thus, there is need for active disclosure of documentation and creation of a level playing field for women in public procurement to maximize the growth of their enterprises [20].

1.3. Local Perspectives on Government Procurement Opportunities

The Government’s Procurement system was originally contained in the Supplies Manual of 1978, which was supplemented by circulars that were issued from time to time by the Treasury. Public procurement in Kenya plays a major role in the utilization of government resources and achievement of the economic development agenda. Kenya’s Vision 2030 and other government policies require public procurement to be carried out in a manner that is not only compliant to established laws and regulations, but also strategic in approach to ensure higher levels of efficiency and effectiveness. In Kenya, the government still face an uphill task in ensuring youth, people living with disabilities and women groups participate in public procurement as they may not have the financial wherewithal [21].

In 2013, the Government of Kenya enforced procurement regulations which began the Access to Government Procurement Opportunities (AGPO) programme, under the National Treasury Public Procurement Directorate. This calls for representation of ‘professional procurement’ in the county’s top leadership to ensure that the nation as a whole leverages upon ‘procurement practice and profession to deliver Kenya Vision 2030 economic development goals and objectives [22]. In the past decades, the public procurement system in Kenya has undergone significant developments. The Public Procurement System in Kenya has evolved from a crude system with no regulations to an orderly legally regulated procurement system.

The benefits of registering for the AGPO includes among others: the ability to participate in 30% of government tenders, to qualify for Local Purchase/Service Orders financing from the Youth/Women Enterprise Development Fund, exclusion from bid bonds, and invoice discounting with financial institutions [23]. The Director of Government Supply Services was responsible for ensuring the proper observance of the provisions of the Manual. The Manual created various tender boards for adjudication of tenders and their awards. Women and other marginalized groups were allowed to procure 30% of public goods and services in line with Article 2 of the PPDR of 2013 and Article 27 of the Constitution of Kenya, 2010, on equality and freedom from discrimination. The sole purpose of the AGPO was to ensure that women and discriminated groups actively participate in public procurement [24].

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In 2013, opportunities for procurement in Government programs emanated from president’s decree that 30% of all opportunities for procurement in government be set aside for WYPD. The AGPO Program was aimed at enabling WYPD-owned enterprises capability of getting involved in government procurement. Nonetheless, AGPO project has been unsuccessful to meet the expectations set by the government. A report by [25] showed that between 2013 and 2016, tenders to the tune of 183.5 billion shillings were listed consisting of 2,232 tenders. Of all these bids, only 172 were awarded to AGPO registered firms. This comprised of only 7.7% of the legally recommended 30%. Therefore, there was a deficit of 22.3% in meeting the threshold of 30% in the period between 2013 and 2016. WYPD are hampered with hindrances to accessing opportunities in government procurement due to that legal, policy and institutional changes affect public procurement domain in Kenya. If the WYPD groups are to access these opportunities, it would mean that

the constraints hampering them from accessing the opportunities is known. This is what this study will seek to determine.

Several studies set to scrutinize the issues affecting realization of AGPO. [26] scrutinized issues hampering admittance to government procurement chances for neglected groups in public institutions. The study examined the consequence of information access, financial support, training and tendering process on access to procurement opportunities. A study was carried out in Nakuru County, Kenya by [27] to investigate the predicaments of accessing government procurement opportunities on tendering involvement by women. [28] scrutinized influence of the achievement of AGPO program on commerce augmentation in youth owned firms in Murang'a south sub-county Kenya. Except for [26] study, other studies have not directly sorted out issues affecting the carrying out of the AGPO program. Consequently, to fill this gap the study investigated the factors affecting access to government procurement opportunities (AGPO) by women, youth and persons with disability in Ol-kalou Sub-County in Kenya.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The study sought to examine the effect of knowledge of tender process on access to government procurement opportunities by women, youths and people living with disability in Ol-kalou sub-county, Kenya.

IV. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

H_{01} : Knowledge of tender process has no statistically significant effect on access to government procurement opportunities by women, youths and people living with disability in Ol-kalou sub-county, Kenya.

V. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

5.1. The Kraljic Portfolio Purchasing Model

Its purpose is to help purchasers maximize supply security and reduce costs, by making the most of their purchasing power. The Kraljic Portfolio Purchasing Model was created by [29] [30]. [29] suggested that selecting the best procurement strategy is a function of the level of supply exposure, technical risk and the strategic nature of the product or service that is its value or cost to the buying firm. In doing so, procurement moves from being a transactional activity to a strategic activity because, as [29] who opined, procurement must become procures management. Despite its age, it's a popular and useful model used in companies worldwide.

These portfolio methods also consist in the need for managers in organizations to develop different procurement methods and strategies for each type of supplier market and each category of purchased item in order for the institutions to comply with guidelines and achieve returns in the procurement management. The procurement portfolio approaches are systematic that enable the evaluation of the strategic significance of a procurement in many ways, as well as the difficulties in managing procurement process. Under Kraljic's approach context, this study's goal is to evaluate factors affecting access to government procurement opportunities for instance contracting of goods and services [31].

The theory of [29] model introduce a procurement portfolio model where procurement of the government is set aside for the disadvantage group in procurement through access to government procurement opportunities (AGPO). This support compliance with procurement regulations as public procurement has been employed as a vital tool for achieving economic, social and other objectives. [32] contend that organizational misbehaviors and non-compliance in procurement. According to [33] the issue of public procurement non-compliance has triggered a lot of debate in recent years approaching.

VI. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Fig 1: Conceptual Framework

VII. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

7.1 Knowledge of Tender Process

Globally, tendering is recognized as a process of making an offer, bid or proposal, or expressing interest in response to an invitation or request for tender. Organizations seek other businesses to respond to a particular need, such as the supply of goods and services, and select an offer or tender that meets their needs and provides the best value for money [34]. In Kenya, it is a requirement that an advertisement on government procurement opportunities be placed in at least three daily newspapers that have wide circulation. Tender advertisements are crucial component of transparency in public procurement and tendering process [35].

Public organizations are usually legally obliged to release tenders for works and services. Regulations vary on whether or not to necessarily award the tender to the lowest bidder, or to award it at all. Within the organization, there are procurement methods by quotation which is done via quotation forms, open tender which is done via media advertisement and closed tender which requires pre- qualifications before the award of the tender. Procurement of the tender has got a systematic process that is followed in determining the tender award (Thomas, 2010). In Kenya, to manage effectively and more efficiently the tendering process, procuring entities through the existing legal framework are required to firstly consolidate departmental procurement plans to provide the entity's corporate procurement plan which before its implementation must get the accounting officer's approval [37].

In 2009 the Public Procurement Oversight Authority (PPOA) estimated that procuring entities were buying at an average of 60% above the prevailing market price, an indicator that public procurement in Kenya does not receive the benefit of competitive procurement [38]. This is in agreement with [39] that the procurement processes have either been marred by huge variations between the price announced at opening of the tender and the price at which the tender was awarded or failure to ensure due diligence in the tendering process. The procurement process in all instances was shrouded in secrecy, inefficiency, corruption and undercutting which resulted in huge amounts of resources going to waste. On the other hand, a study by [40] established that despite the efforts made by the PPOA to strengthen the public procurement system in Kenya, a number of tendering processes in the public sector are marred with general gross inefficiency while [41] revealed that tendering process was riddled with delays in terms of time due to a lot of documentation required, cost overruns and compromised quality of works; this makes the whole process tedious and challenging.

A survey done by National Treasury (2015) showed that 30 per cent of the state corporations award tenders fairly while 14 per cent are involved in procurement malpractices. The treasury indicated that emphasis on e-involved procurement system is to ensure transparency in how tenders were awarded. Estimates by the Treasury showed that the government losses more than Sh70 billion annually due to fraudulent manipulations in procurement process [42]. KenGen was ranked among top ten public sectors associated with procurement manipulations. Data from World Bank show that KenGen lost 5 Billion relating to procurement and tendering malpractices [43]. According to [44] KenGen is said to have illegally awarded a Chinese firm a tender worth 8 billion contrary to tendering system guidelines.

Empowerment programs planned at the national and at global level are gradually focusing on women and youth to chip in public procurement. Information awareness and the mobilized awareness remarkably contribute to involvement of youth and women in government tenders [45]. The commencement of awareness among the WYPD, they are accomplished to partake of the government tenders. Such awareness on the tender process augments more trade projections, enhanced information systems more often than not using internet for services and products through traditions and standards of quality contemporary to doing business in the government can aid in enhancing the efficiency of WYPD during competition for government contracts with prominent great players [45]. In addition, Jamii Bora in Kenya is conducting training to the WYPD on how to tender for government contracts [26].

The most advocated interaction between access to information on procurement and WYPD access to procurement opportunities in government is contingent on the fact that not having information on presence of the openings, these underprivileged groups may not gain from the splendid program. In fact, enhanced information systems by and large throughout the internet for services and product purchasing using up to date standards of quality and the best industry practices in the government has the potential to help advance the adroitness of supplies within the special group's as they try to win government tender opportunities with well-endowed personalities [46].

7.2 Government Procurement Opportunities by YWPD

Through the AGPO which is a YWPD procurement scheme, the Jubilee Party during presidential repeat election made a pledge to ensure that KShs. 6 billion is apportioned to the youths and women groups. The principles of Uwezo Fund are economic growth stimulation, accessibility, Representation and Accountability. Representation insinuates the guarantee that the involvement of Kenyans in general including WYPD, representatives elected to parliament and analogous government officials [32].

The main objective of the program of AGPO is to provide a guarantee that all enterprises owned by YWPD partake in procurement in public institutions. Tenders in the government each fiscal year amounts to billions hence this is a very fertile opportunity for the YWPD (RoK, 2013). Conventions for procurement in 2013 were custom made to guarantee that the contracts granted to the YWPD amounted to 30% of the total contracts devoid of competition from conventional highly regarded firms [47].

[48] recognized that the set of laws states that a procuring entity must assign at least 30% of its expenditure in procurement for the sole reason of procuring products, works and services to disadvantaged groups' owned firms. The standard for this allotment is anchored on conformity with AGPO set of laws. Registration and pre-qualification of YWPD owned enterprises is conducted for essential establishment of accessibility to contracts and tenders by the government.

A study that was undertaken by [20] asserts that public procuring establishments express procurement information through public advertisements as insisted on the 2005 disposal and procurement in Public Act and subsequent legislation. Conversely, with the fiscal restrictions, countless advertise only once in two pronounced newspapers and by so doing, most of the, to be suppliers may not be aware of procurement proceedings. The study determined that one of the hindrances is advertising through the newspapers, because of the everyday expenditure incurred in putting up the advert on the papers. Publishing of tenders is viewed to be a costly exercise, the public procuring establishments would as an alternative advertise once on the papers, though tender advertisements are a vital factor of lucidity in procurement in public parastatals and the process of tendering. The other additional impediment relates to inappropriate education for WYPDs, which is a hindrance to taking part in entrepreneurial endeavors. So the study commends the government to use other avenues to relay information.

As hypothesized by [49], procurement is the fundamental function that formulates the actions and processes to obtain products and services. High level of transparency, accountability and value for money in the consumption of a procurement budget is seen through effective preparations done by public procurement mechanisms. They are vital to poverty eradication and also help in effectiveness. [50] noted that improving the effectiveness, adeptness and transparency of procurement systems is a going concern of governments and of the global development community. Public procurement is ever identified as a machinery of policy in government as well as a pedal for broad social, economic and environmental transformation. A lot of issues have been raised as having involvement to women and youth engagement in public procurement. One of the issues is the legal/regulatory structure. The legal and regulatory framework creates the rules within which all the financial institutions, instruments, and markets carry out procurement procedures in a particular country [51].

VIII. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Descriptive research design was employed as the study's research design. Descriptive research is undertaken to enable the description of the current situation, what people presently believe, what they are doing at currently and so forth [52]. This study's target population were members of various groups belonging to women youths and persons with disabilities. There are a total of 203 women, 64 youth and 14 people with disability groups in Ol-Kalou Sub-County. As such the total target population was 281 women, youth and persons with disability groups in Ol-kalou Sub- County. Hence these comprised the study's target population. The study adopted simple random sampling where 165 respondents were chosen to act as the respondents of the study. The study used data drawn from primary sources. As such, the study primarily used a structured questionnaire constructed on a 5-point Likert Scale to collect data. The questionnaire contained close ended statements relating to the study variables. Reliability and validity was established for standardization of the structured questionnaires that was used in the study. The researcher captured both qualitative and quantitative data and this data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings were presented using tables and discussions thereof.

IX. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

9.1 Response Rate

Out of 165 questionnaires distributed to the respondents for the purposes of data collection, 101 of them were returned. This constitutes 61.2% of the total response rate. According to Babbie and Mouton (2002) a response rate of above 50% is adequate for analysis thus a response rate of 61.2% in this study was considered adequate.

9.2 Descriptive Statistics

9.2.1 Knowledge of Tender Process Descriptive Statistics

The study established the views of the respondents regarding knowledge of tender process by computing the percentages, means and standard deviations of their responses. The findings from the analysis were as presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1: Descriptive Statistics on Knowledge of Tender Process

	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev
We as a group always get to know when the government procurement adverts are out	21.8	23.8	4.0	21.8	28.7	2.88	1.577
We are able to access government procurement adverts on government's notice boards	15.8	34.7	3.0	18.8	27.7	2.92	1.514
Information about government procurement opportunities are easily available in chiefs office within the sub-county	11.9	18.8	4.0	22.8	42.6	2.35	1.479
We are able to access booklets and brochures with information about government procurement opportunities	17.8	21.8	5.0	29.7	25.7	2.76	1.491
We are able to acquire newspapers where government procurement opportunities are advertised	34.7	28.7	4.0	18.8	13.9	3.51	1.474
We obtain application forms from the government sub-county offices	5.9	18.8	7.9	20.8	46.5	2.17	1.350
The application forms are made simple thus enabling us to be able to fill them easily	7.9	29.7	8.9	24.8	28.7	2.63	1.376
The government sometimes avails the application forms through their website where we easily download them	13.9	49.5	8.9	12.9	14.9	3.35	1.292
We know how to fill the applications forms for the tender application	32.7	30.7	5.9	17.8	12.9	3.52	1.432
Valid N (listwise)	101						

Respondents disagreed that them as a group always get to know when the government procurement adverts are out. 50.5% of the respondents disagreed registering a mean of 2.88 and a standard deviation of 1.577. Further, 50.5% of the respondents strongly and/or agreed that they are able to access government procurement adverts on government's notice boards. This had a mean of 2.92 and a standard deviation of 1.514. They also disagreed that information about government procurement opportunities are easily available in chiefs' office within the sub-county. 42.6% of the respondents strongly disagreed while 22.8% of them disagreed having a mean of 2.35 and a standard deviation of 1.479. Results also described that respondents were in disagreement that they able to access booklets and brochures with information about government procurement opportunities where 29.7% of the respondents disagreed while 25.7% of them strongly disagreed registering a mean of 2.76 and a standard deviation of 1.491. A mean of 3.51 and a standard deviation of 1.474 were recorded where respondents agreed that they are able to acquire newspapers where government procurement opportunities are advertised. 34.7% of the respondents agreed while 28.7% of them strongly agreed. Respondents disagreed that (M=2.17, SD=1.350) that they obtain application forms from the government sub-county offices where 46.5% and 20.8% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively. It was also observed that respondents disagreed with the statement that the application forms are made simple thus enabling them to fill them easily. 53.5% of the respondents strongly and/or disagreed registering a mean of 2.63 and a standard deviation of 1.376. On the other hand, respondents agreed that the government sometimes avails the application forms through their website where they easily download them. 49.5% of the respondents agreed while 13.9% of them strongly agreed recording a mean of 3.35 and a standard deviation of 1.292. Further, they agreed that they know how to fill the applications forms for the tender application. 32.7% and 30.7% of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively having a mean of 3.52 and a standard deviation of 1.432.

9.2.2 Government Procurement Opportunities Descriptive Results

Respondents’ views regarding government procurement opportunities were sought. Responses in regard to Likert scale items on government procurement opportunities were as shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2: Descriptive Statistics on Access to Government Procurement Opportunities

	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean	Std. Dev
We have been supplying to the government through acquisition of tenders	18.8	8.9	4.0	36.6	31.7	2.47	1.487
Since we have acquired government LPOs, we are given priorities in all AGPO projects	16.8	8.9	3.0	32.7	38.6	2.33	1.484
Having been classified as among WYPD groups, we get prioritized in government tenders	10.9	12.9	7.9	32.7	35.6	2.31	1.368
We have found the allocation of tenders for AGPO programs to be a very transparent process	9.9	8.9	7.9	27.7	45.5	2.10	1.338
We have always been given a convincing explanation as to why we obtain or fail to obtain a given tender	5.0	17.8	7.9	29.7	39.6	2.19	1.271
We are of the opinion that tendering for AGPO projects is enshrined in a lot of secrecy	32.7	9.9	12.9	22.8	21.8	3.09	1.588
Being among special groups has been a key advantage for us accessing AGPO tenders	10.9	13.9	6.9	36.6	31.7	2.36	1.346
We feel that we are fully engaged in government procurement opportunities	8.9	7.9	5.9	36.6	40.6	2.08	1.262
Valid N (listwise)	100						

I.

Results indicated that respondents disagreed that they have been supplying to the government through acquisition of tenders where 36.6% of the respondents disagreed whereas and 31.7% of them strongly disagreed registering a mean of 2.47 and a standard deviation of 1.487. Further, respondents disagreed with the statement that since they have acquired government LPOs, they are given priorities in all AGPO projects. 38.6% and 32.7% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively registering a mean of 2.33 and a standard deviation of 1.484. Additionally, with a mean of 2.31 and a standard deviation of 1.368, 68.3% of the respondents strongly and/or disagreed that having been classified as among WYPD groups, they get prioritized in government tenders. 45.5% of the respondents strongly disagreed while 27.7% of them disagreed that they have found the allocation of tenders for AGPO programs to be a very transparent process. This had a mean of 2.10 and a standard deviation of 1.338. The study established that respondents disagreed that they have always been given a convincing explanation as to why they obtain or fail to obtain a given tender. 39.6% and 29.7% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively recording a mean of 2.19 and a standard deviation of 1.271. On the other hand, respondents were not sure on whether they are of the opinion that tendering for AGPO projects is enshrined in a lot of secrecy. 42.6% of the respondents agreed, 12.9% of them were uncertain while 44.6% of the respondents disagreed. This registered a mean of 3.09 and a standard deviation of 1.588. On contrary, respondents disagreed that being among special groups has been a key advantage for them accessing AGPO tenders. 36.6% and 31.7% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively registering a mean of 2.36 and a standard deviation of 1.346. Also, respondents disagreed that they feel that they are fully engaged in government procurement opportunities where 40.6% of the respondents strongly disagreed while 36.6% of them disagreed recording a mean of 2.08 and a standard deviation of 1.262.

9.3 Correlation Analysis

The composite scores for the independent variable was correlated with the composite scores for the dependent variable. Pearson product moment correlation coefficient was used for the analysis. The findings from the analysis were presented as shown in table 3.

Table 3: Correlations between Knowledge of Tender Process and Access Government Procurement Opportunities

		Knowledge of Tender Process
Access to Government Procurement Opportunities	Pearson Correlation	.429**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	101

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

From the results an average positive significant ($r=.429, p=.000$) relationship between knowledge of tender process and access to government procurement opportunities. This showed that knowledge of tender process had a significant impact on access to government procurement process. This therefore, indicates that knowledge of tender process significantly affected access to government procurement opportunities. These findings agreed with the findings of [46] who posited that enhanced information systems by and large throughout the internet for services and product purchasing using up to date standards of quality and the best industry practices in the government has the potential to help advance the adroitness of supplies within the special group’s as they try to win government tender opportunities with well-endowed personalities.

9.4 Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis for the study H_{01} observed that knowledge of tender process has no statistical effect on access to government procurement opportunities by WYPD in county governments in Ol-kalou Sub-County, Kenya. To ascertain this hypothesis, ANOVA was used to either reject or fail to reject the hypothesis. The findings from the analysis were as presented in the tables below.

TABLE 4: Model Summary for Knowledge of Tender Process

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.429 ^a	.184	.176	.83974

a. Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge of Tender Process

From the findings, an R-squared value of .184 was established. This indicated that knowledge of tender process can significantly account for up to 18.4% of the total variance in access to government procurement opportunities by disadvantaged groups. As such, knowledge of tender process contributed to a small extent on access to government procurement opportunities. The analysis of variance yielded the results shown in table 5.

TABLE 5: ANOVA^a for Knowledge of Tender Process

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	15.723	1	15.723	22.296	.000 ^b
	Residual	69.812	99	.705		
	Total	85.534	100			

a. Dependent Variable: Access to Government Procurement Opportunities

b. Predictors: (Constant), Knowledge of Tender Process

Findings from the analysis of variance gave an F-Value ($F_{(1, 99)} = 22.296, p=.000$) which was found to be statistically significant at $p<.05$ level of significance. Therefore the researcher observed that knowledge of tender process have a significant effect on access to government procurement opportunities. Consequently, the first hypothesis H_{01} that

Knowledge of tender process has no statistical effect on access to government procurement opportunities by WYPD in county governments in Ol-kalou Sub-County, Kenya was rejected.

X. CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The study concluded that the knowledge of tender process has a significant effect on access to government procurement opportunities by WYPD. Findings indicated that knowledge of tender process and government procurement opportunities have a significant relationship with each other. As such, the researcher observed that knowledge of tender process play a significant role in determining access to government procurement opportunities. Therefore, knowledge of the tender process plays a significant role in determining the access to government procurement opportunity.

XI. RECOMMENDATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study recommended that the county government enhance its communication channels to facilitate the access of information regarding governments' tenders. Respondents expressed difficulties in accessing governments tendering information unless they visit the notice boards or acquire newspapers. In this age of technology the study recommends that the county can make use of current technology to easily relay information to be accessed by all stakeholders. This improvement will go a long way in enhancing access to government procurement opportunities by disadvantaged groups in Ol-kalou sub-county in Kenya. The knowledge of the tender process was depicted to have a significant effect on access to government procurement opportunities. Hence enhancing communication channels to enable this knowledge to be passed across enhances disadvantaged groups' chances of accessing government procurement opportunities.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Blome, C. & Schoenherr, T. (2011). "Supply chain risk management in financial crises: A multiple case study approach", *An International Journal of Production Economics*, 134(1); 43– 57.
- [2.] World Bank (WB) (2010). Project Procurement - Policies, Guidelines, Documents for Projects Retrieved from: <http://www.worldbank.org>.
- [3.] Tukamuhabwa B. (2012). Antecedents and Consequences of Public Procurement Noncompliance Behavior. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 4(1) 34-46.
- [4.] Ndolo, J. & Njagi, E. (2014). Role of ethics in procurement process effectiveness in the water sector in Kenya :(A case study of EWASCO Embu County). *International Journal of supply chain management*.
- [5.] Schiavo-Campo, S. & Sundaram, P. (2000). To serve and Preserve: Improving Public Administration in a Competitive World.(Available online at: http://www.adb.org/documents/manuals/serve_and_preserve/default.asp). Accessed on 23rd January, 2007.
- [6.] Arrowsmith, S. (2010). Public Procurement Regulation: An introduction, *The Public Procurement Research Group*, University of Nottingham, United Kingdom
- [7.] Callender, G. & Mathews, D. (2000)."Government Purchasing: An evolving Profession?" *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting and financial management*, 12(2), 272-290.
- [8.] Kennekae, L. (2012). Procurement strategies to serve the public good. Principal Procurement Specialist, Public Procurement and Asset Disposal Board, Government of Botswana.
- [9.] Schapper, R., Veiga Malta, N., & Gilbert, D. (2006). An Analytical Framework for the Management and Reform of Public Procurement. *Journal of Public Procurement*, 6(1&3), 1-26.
- [10.] Mahmood, I. (2010). Public procurement and corruption in Bangladesh confronting the challenges and opportunities. *Journal of public administration and policy research*. 2(6)103-111
- [11.] Teixeira, R. (2012). The Brazilian Experience of Using Public Procurement Policies to Promote the Development of Micro and Small Enterprises from the Legal Point of View. *Attorney and Professor in International Law at University of Sao Paulo School of Law*.
- [12.] Kumar, V. (2011), 'Constitution Amendment Bill defeated; Lokpal Bill passed', *The Hindu*, 27 December, available at: www.thehindu.com/news/national/article2752837.ece (accessed 21 May 2013).
- [13.] Kachwaha, S (2009). 'India: Public Procurement - India', *mondaq*, available at: www.mondaq.com/article.asp?articleid=80200 (accessed 21 May 2013).

- [14.] Kirton, J. (2013). "G20-G8 Partnership in Global Economic Governance." Background paper for a conference on "From the G8 to the G20 and Beyond: Setting a Course for Economic Global Governance," Chatham House, London, May 9. <http://www.g8.utoronto.ca/scholar/kirton-chathamhouse-2013.html>.
- [15.] Mota, F. & Filho, J. (2011). 'Public e-procurement and the duality of technology: a comparative study in the context of Brazil and Paraíba', *Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management*, 8(2); 315-330.
- [16.] Basheka, C. & Bisangabasaija, E. (2010). Determinants of unethical public procurement in local government systems of Uganda: a case study. *Int. J. Procurement Manage*, 3(1); 91-104.
- [17.] Frøystad, M., Heggstad, K. & Fjeldstad, O. (2010). Linking procurement and political economy. *UK Department for International Development and the World Bank Institute*.
- [18.] Ambe, I. & Badenhorst-Weiss, J. (2011). "An exploration of public sector supply chains with specific reference to the South African situation", *Journal of Public Administration*, 46(3): 1100-1115.
- [19.] Public Procurement Authority: Electronic Bulletin, (2011). Public Procurement Act, 2003 (Act 663). Accra: Public Procurement Board.
- [20.] Puddephatt, A. & Kaspar, L. (2012). Benefits of Transparency in Public Procurement for SMEs. London: Harper Collins Publishers.
- [21.] Orodho, J., (2013). *Essentials of Educational and Social Science Research methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Nairobi Acts Press
- [22.] Mwangi, N. (2017). Determinants of Compliance with Access to Government Procurement Opportunities Regulations for Special Groups by Public Universities in Kenya. Unpublished Doctorate Thesis of Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology
- [23.] Amemba, L., Nyaboke, P., Osoro, A. & Mburu, N. (2013) Challenges affecting public procurement performance process in Kenya. *International Journal of Research in Management*.3(4).
- [24.] Onsongo E., Okioga, C., Otieno, R. & Mongare, O. (2012) .Challenges facing procurement committees in implementing the procurement act. A case of secondary schools procurement committees in Kisii County. *Unpublished MBA Report*
- [25.] Transparency International Annual Report, 2012-2013 (II). (2014). Public Procurement in Kenya: Cash Cow for the Corrupt or Enabler for Public Service Delivery? Adili, 145.
- [26.] Ngure, G. & Simba, T. (2015) Factors Affecting Access To Government Procurement Opportunities for Disadvantaged Groups in Public Entities: (A Case Study Of Kenya Ports Authority) *International Journal of Science and Research* 4(10) 745-755.
- [27.] Korir, N. & Wanambiro, V. (2017). Influence of Access to Government Procurement Opportunities on Tendering Participation by Women in Nakuru County. Unpublished Master Thesis Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology.
- [28.] Sumab, G. (2015). *Influence of the implementation of access to government procurement opportunities programme on business growth in youth owned enterprises in Murang'a south sub county, Kenya*. Unpublished Master Thesis University of Nairobi.
- [29.] Kraljic, P. (1983). Purchasing must become supply management. *Harvard Business Review*, 61(5), 109-117
- [30.] Van Weele, A, (2005), *Purchasing and Supply Chain Management*, 4th edition
- [31.] Van Weele, A.J. (2002). *Purchasing and Supply Chain Management. Analysis, Planning and Practice*, 3rd edition, Thomson Learning, London.
- [32.] Karjalainen, K., Katariina, K. & Erik, M. (2009). On-Compliant Work Behaviour in Purchasing: An Exploration of Reasons behind Maverick Buying. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 85; 245-261.
- [33.] Tukamuhabwa B. (2012). Antecedents and Consequences of Public Procurement Noncompliance Behavior. *Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies*, 4(1) 34-46.
- [34.] Wogube, S. (2011). Procurement Planning and Services Delivery in Public Enterprises.

- [35.] Kathure, B. N. (2012). Challenges faced by small and medium enterprises suppliers when bidding for tenders: A case of Thika District. *International Journal of Academy Research in Business and Social Sciences* 3 (12).
- [36.] Thomas, P. (2010). Disability, poverty and the millennium development goals: Relevance, challenges and Opportunities for DFID, Disability KAR Programme.
- [37.] Kendo, E., & Getuno, P. (2016). "Factors Affecting Tendering Process In State Corporations: A Case Of Kenya Literature Bureau". *International Journal of Current Business and Social Sciences*, 1(5), 415-428.
- [38.] PPOA (2009). The Long Term Policy Framework for Public Procurement in Kenya, Draft Zero; UNESS.
- [39.] Transparency International Annual Report, 2012-2013 (TI). (2014). Public Procurement in Kenya: Cash Cow for the Corrupt or Enabler for Public Service Delivery? Adili, 145.
- [40.] Kadima, R. Musiega, D., Kibet, Y., & Manase, G. (2013). An analysis of procurement procedures on the implementation of Government construction projects in Kenyan public universities: Case study of Masinde Muliro University. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*. 2 (11), 23-29.
- [41.] Mutava, C. (2012). Impact of public procurement procedures on delivery of maintenance works; Case of The Ministry of Housing, National Social Security Fund and Kenyatta National Hospital Maintenance Projects. Unpublished MA Project, University of Nairobi.
- [42.] Wanzala O. (2015). "World Bank raises concern on quality of Kenya's graduates". Daily Nation, October 1.
- [43.] World Bank (WB) (2012). Project Procurement - Policies, Guidelines, Documents for Projects Retrieved from: <http://www.worldbank.org>.
- [44.] Kisero, J. (2005). KenGen curious tender award. Business Daily, Nairobi.
- [45.] Mentzer, J., (2011): Defining Supply Chain Management, in: *Journal of Business* Institute of Economic Affairs-Kenya. (2008). *Profile of Women's Socio-Economic Status in Kenya*.
- [46.] Kisurkat, E. (2016). Effects of Tendering on Organizational Performance: A Survey of Public Institutions in Kajiado County. Unpublished Master Thesis University of Africa.
- [47.] Gatere, C. & Shale, I. (2014). Challenges affecting the implementation of access to government procurement opportunities for special interest groups in Kenya : A case of Nairobi County. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Entrepreneurship*, 1(12),831- 847.
- [48.] Ngeno, J., Namusonge, G., & Nteere, K. (2014). Effect of discriminatory public procurement practices on organizational performance: A survey of public sector corporations in Kenya. *Global Journal of Commerce and Management Perspective*, 3(4).
- [49.] Schapper, R., Veiga Malta, N., & Gilbert, D. (2006). An Analytical Framework for the Management and Reform of Public Procurement. *Journal of Public Procurement*, 6(1&3), 1-26.
- [50.] OECD (2010). *The impact of institutional investors on OECD financial markets*, Financial Market trends, 68.
- [51.] OECD. (2007). Integrity in Public Procurement Good Practice from A to Z, OECD Publishing, Paris, France Commonwealth Secretariat, Commonwealth Youth Programme. *Commonwealth Plan of Action for Youth Empowerment (PAYE) 2007-2015*.
- [52.] Baumgartner, T., Heinrichs, M., Vonlanthen, A., Fischbacher, U., & Fehr, E. (2008). Oxytocin shapes the neural circuitry of trust and trust adaptation in humans. *Neuron*, 58; 639-650.